

Table 2. Agronomic characters of rice plants from *Striga* infested and noninfested fields (n = 24). Ishurdi, Bangladesh, 1987.

Character	Noninfested	Infested	t-value ^a
Plant ht (cm)	82.57	46.52	10.60***
Fresh plant wt (g)	7.92	3.71	2.86**
Leaf length (cm)	36.11	24.32	10.57***
Internodes (no./plant)	3.08	2.00	5.56***
Internode length (cm)	8.64	3.14	6.39***
Stage of development	Maturing Panicle	No flag leaf	-

^a Significant at 0.1% (***) and 1% (**) levels.

mid-July, the parasite populations consisted of plants with mature fruits that were disseminating seed as well as plants in early and late juvenile stages of growth. The minute seeds of the parasite possess prolonged dormancy and can germinate across a very long period, making control by physical and chemical means difficult.

When a sugarcane crop is destroyed by the parasite, farmers usually grow rice in the *Striga*-infested fields, enabling the parasite to establish and parasitize rice as well. Because rice is much more widely cultivated than sugarcane, the

parasite is getting a choice of two hosts and there is a greater chance of it spreading to other areas of the country. Nongraminaceous crops, especially legumes and jute, are recommended for infested fields to avoid crop loss and parasite dissemination during the dry season. □

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Soil and Crop Management

Efficiency of urea supergranule (USG) under water stress at different growth stages

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Rice crops in most farming situations of northwest India are subjected to moisture stress during some growth stages, depending on rainfall and

Effect on yield of USG under water stress at different growth stages.^a Pantnagar, India, 1984-85.

Growth stage stress ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	Jaya, 1984		Pant Dhan 4, 1985	
	USG	Urea	USG	Urea
Early tillering (0-15 DT)	-	-	-	-
Active tillering (16-30 DT)	-	-	-	-
Advanced tillering (31-45 DT)	-	-	-	-
Near panicle initiation (46-60 DT)	-	-	-	-
Panicle initiation to flowering (61-90 DT)	-	-	-	-
Stress	6.0	5.7	4.7	4.1
- Stress	5.9	5.5	5.2	4.9
- - Stress	6.0	5.3	4.8	4.6
- - - Stress	5.9	5.6	5.2	4.8
- - - - Stress	6.2	5.6	NT	NT
Stress Stress	5.5	4.5	4.6	4.4
- Stress Stress	NT	NT	4.7	4.4
- - Stress Stress	5.6	5.6	4.8	4.9
- - - Stress Stress	5.4	4.9	4.9	4.5
Rainfed throughout crop period				
		LSD 5%	LSD 5%	
N carrier		0.3	0.2	
Water stress		0.6	0.4	
Interaction		ns	ns	
CV (%)		9.7	6.5	
Seeding date		12 Jun	1 Jun	
Transplanting date		17 Jul	11 Jul	

^a DT = days after transplanting, NT = not tried. ^b - = no water stress, stress = saturation during rains and about 20% depletion of available moisture during rainless periods.

and 2,033 mm in 1985. Rainfall distribution and pan evaporation are shown in the figure. The experiment was a split-plot design with four replications.

One month moisture stress during advanced tillering to panicle initiation resulted in a USG performance no better than that of urea (see table). In all other moisture stress treatments, including rainfed, USG was superior to urea. □

Weekly total rainfall and USWB pan evaporation (mm)

Weekly rainfall and USWB pan evaporation during the crop season. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1984-85.

irrigation. We compared efficiency of urea supergranules (USG) and urea effects on yield under varying periods of water stress at different growth stages in 1984-85 field trials. Soil was silt loam Aquic Hapludoll (pH 7.9, 1.8% organic matter, CEC 20 meq/100 g soil, 29% field capacity, and 10% permanent wilting point). Available soil water in the root zone was 100 mm. Total rainfall during the season was 1,377 mm in 1984